

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D3.6

Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

October 2021

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UPS	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
Mx	Month x
MS	Milestone
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report (D3.6) outlines the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy for the MES-CoBraD project. It acts as a reference point for how each stakeholder group can be understood, approached, and engaged throughout the course of the project. In addition, actions are established to begin a successful starting point for creating meaningful engagement.

The primary objective of MES-CoBraD (Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders) is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols, in light of the MES-CoBraD Agreement and associated challenges.

To do so, MES-CoBraD will co-develop with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. Stakeholder engagement is essential to actualise the expected outputs and the resulting impacts, to fully realise the proposed societal benefits. Therefore, this strategy takes the following approach to ensure that these aims are met.

The first chapter discusses the methodology which was used to assist the production of this document. It explains in detail how a survey and meetings were used to help understand each of stakeholder categories which were identified at the project's conception. The decisions to take this course of action are also justified. Following this, an overview of the results from the survey are charted.

Following this, a section outlines each stakeholder group. These are presented as the basis of the engagement strategy, to ensure a targeted approach which meets project KPIs. For each category a landscape analysis is presented to describe the group, this is followed by key messages to stimulate engagement, and finally suggested engagement methods appropriate to this group are outlined.

Chapter three centres on cross stakeholder activities. This demonstrates how certain synergies between stakeholder groups can be explored to facilitate new conversations and broader engagement. These linkages are connected to a proposed series of interactive engagement events to make the connections meaningful, allowing groups the opportunity to engage and contribute to the project.

Chapter four begins to clarify the implementation and management of stakeholder engagement activities. The first section shows how four cross stakeholder events will be approached, and the second section details how each engagement activity should be recorded and reported on to ensure accurate overviews of engagement are maintained.

The final chapter outlines possible risks associated with the execution of the strategy, as well as means to minimise these potential issues. This section touches on project complexity, stakeholder diversity, COVID-19, and European legislation on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The deliverable closes with a summary and a short description of coming plans relating to stakeholder engagement.

1 METHODOLOGY

1.1 OVERVIEW

As outlined in the DoA, the stakeholder engagement strategy is a necessary component of the project's success, allowing maximum impact by engaging groups and communities that are linked and connected to the project. Stakeholder engagement will account for the project's multidisciplinary basis by acknowledge this across stakeholder categories and geographies. Although the project will develop and grow as outputs and results are produced, the stakeholder groups will remain the same and the initial landscape acts as a starting point of how to approach these groups. From the point on, the following strategy will act as a living document to be added to if relevant and applicable information and strategies emerge to allow greater exploitation of the project and its links to stakeholders. To achieve these aims, a methodical approach to developing the strategy was implemented.

To formulate a relevant, robust and workable stakeholder engagement strategy, a two-stage methodology was employed, following provisions already made at the proposal stage, to properly consult all project beneficiaries. Initially an internal survey was designed, updated and distributed throughout the consortium, acting as the first stage of consultation. Following this, meetings were held at WP level to build on the information gleaned in the survey.

Taking this approach guaranteed that each partner participated in the development of this strategy, providing their input and taking ownership of relevant upcoming engagement activities, and therefore the resulting outcomes are catered to the project, the project partners and their activities, as well as the main stakeholder groups, as identified at the stage of the proposal. As a result, the suggested strategic engagement activities in this document are built through the input and consultation of those who will look to implement them.

The following section outlines why and how these methods were taken.

1.2 SURVEY

1.2.1 AIMS AND DETAILS

The Stakeholder Engagement survey was designed to map the overall stakeholder landscape throughout the MES-CoBraD project and its related activities. The aim was to understand how each beneficiary, as an individual organisation, but also within the context of MES-CoBraD WPs and tasks, viewed their relationships with key stakeholder groups, as identified at the proposal stage, and discern in what ways they intend to engage these groups. Furthermore, with mapping the existing connections, the data also highlighted what channels, tools, and skills were already in place to support engagement with stakeholders. This formed a clear picture of what existing links, connections, and strategies could be built upon, and, in addition, it identified gaps and opportunities to maximise the impact of the project beyond what beneficiaries originally planned.

The survey also charted upcoming engagement activities that were not specifically mentioned in the DoA but occur due to the needs of each WP as the project implementation begun.

Before the survey was shared, a draft was reviewed by partners involved in T3.1. After their feedback had been incorporated, the questionnaire was disseminated throughout the consortium to collect an initial analysis and draw understanding about the stakeholder landscape within the project.

The survey was open for two weeks, from 15/06/21 – 29/06/21. The survey contained 50 questions and respondents were required to complete questions covering four main sections: 1) Stakeholder identification; 2) Stakeholder engagement; 3) Training; and 4) Opportunity based communication. The final section, opportunity-based communications, was mainly included to collect information for MileStone 3 (MS3) of WP9. For more details about the survey, the full document is included in annex 1.

1.2.2 RESULTS

At least one representative from each of the project’s 14 beneficiaries completed the questionnaire, amounting to a total of 16 responses. In the following, each of the four main survey sections will be presented and the main results documented.

Stakeholder Identification: Respondents were asked to list which stakeholder groups they planned to engage with the project activities associated with their workload. As the graph (figure 1) indicates, researchers are the group which are planned to have the most engagement being mentioned by 14 of the 16 respondents.

3 of 16 respondents (18.75%) wish to engage vulnerable groups (e.g., refugees, disabled persons) across the course of the project.

Figure 1 Targeted stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Engagement: When asked which engagement activities were planned, respondents selected from a list of pre-selected methods and closed discussion groups and email consultations were most popular, each selected by 11 of the 16 respondents. Figure 2 shows the full break down of results.

Figure 2 Planned methods of engagement

As a follow up, respondents were asked about the frequency with which they needed to engage with stakeholder groups. The results to this question are detailed in figure 3, below.

Figure 3 Frequency of contact

Training: Four of the 16 respondents have a provision for training stakeholders which relates to their research, results, and services as part of WPs and/or tasks. As a follow up question, four additional respondents indicated a need for training activities as part of their WPs and/or tasks but they have no provision to provide this. This training mainly relates to training on the platform that will be developed by the project.

Opportunity-based communication: Across the 16 survey responses, 20 international conferences were identified that were felt to be relevant for the project i.e., opportunity for attendance, presentations, co-located events.

When listing existing channels for communication, 12 respondents flagged their social media channels as a communication tool. For full results see figure 4, below. The other options include website, personal contacts, media, and lectures.

Figure 4 Existing communication methods

The information gathered within the survey has informed the content of this document. In the following sections, repeated reference will be made to the survey’s findings.

1.2.3 FOLLOW-UP MEETINGS: WORK PACKAGE LEAD LEVEL

To build on the survey data, nine follow up meetings were conducted with WP leaders between 07/07/21 – 02/09/21. The meetings explored the survey responses and developed an understanding of existing stakeholder networks and highlighted engagement methods, including competencies and experience of these. Finally, the sessions created dialogue, providing beneficiaries the opportunity to ask questions and hear about the development and proposals for the stakeholder engagement strategy.

Conversations were held with WP leaders for greater focus on engagement needs– what stakeholder groups are relevant and what methods are needed –within specific work streams. This provided an overall picture per WP and allowed respective leaders to discuss what stakeholders were important for their WP. In turn, it was discussed what opportunities there were within tasks and deliverables for further engagement and gain understanding if such ideas were possible/desirable.

These meetings lasted between 20 and 40 minutes. They took a largely informal structure, first discussing the survey responses and then questions turned to focus on WP activities. Notes were taken and incorporated into the development of this document. The information gathered during these meetings has helped shape this document and tailor the strategies of engagement to project partners and project activities.

2 ENGAGEMENT OF STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

2.1 OVERVIEW

In the following section, the above methodology will be deployed to build the strategy for each stakeholder group, as identified at the proposal phase of the MES-CoBraD project and, later, the DoA. Additional knowledge and input from task 3.1 leader (LIBER) will use this information to propose recommendations and suggestions for engagement activities.

To ensure the work of the MES-CoBraD project is actualised at its fullest potential, engagement with stakeholder groups is essential. The project has an important role to bring stakeholders to the table, allowing its outputs to shape discussions, and bring about change to political and scientific communities, as well as the health outcomes of patients. A coherent strategy of how to engage with stakeholders – in conjunction with the project’s communication and dissemination strategy (D9.1) – is a vital component in achieving these ends.

At the project’s proposal phase, 12 stakeholder groups were identified. Early identification of the main communities who could benefit and contribute to the project allowed an instant focus for communications, dissemination, and engagement activities, prior to this landscape analysis and engagement strategy. The stakeholder groups are as follows: 1) researchers; 2) research producing organisations; 3) research funders; 4) research libraries; 5) industry; 6) policy makers; 7) citizen scientists; 8) research infrastructures and e-infrastructures; 9) health providers; 10) patients and patient advocates; 11) general public; and 12) other groups.

Throughout the rest of this section, each stakeholder group will be discussed. First a description of that group’s characteristics will be presented, followed by the messages which are relevant for this group. This leads into a closing description of the proposed methods of engagement for this particular stakeholder group.

By outlining the groups characteristics – as part of the landscape section – a greater understanding of the dynamics and needs of that target group’s make up will enable a more focused and targeted approach to engagement. Before engagement activities are proposed, a concise and clear message to pitch to specific stakeholders’ group will help promote and attract their participation. This section is important as their involvement, and their understanding of the project’s worth, cannot be expected as a prerequisite. Finally, engagement activities will be proposed which are relevant for that stakeholder group. These suggestions will allow consortium members to fine tune and adjust their outreach efforts in a planned and coordinated manner. Work outlined within the DOA must be completed as outlined. However, the intention of this document and its engagement suggestions is to develop the project’s engagement output and maximise its impact by reaching all stakeholder groups in a strategic manner.

To practically support the strategic aims of this document, and its future implementation, an internal database of stakeholders will support the implementation of this strategy. The database will evolve throughout the project and it aims to ensure that relevant groups are identified and logged, and those that engage continue to do so. The information stored will include contact details of those engaged. To manage this overview in accordance with GDPR, the project’s legal and ethical helpdesk (see D2.1 Legal and Ethical Helpdesk) will be contacted and collaborated with.

2.2 ENGAGEMENT METHODS

Engagement activities focus on creating a dialogue between project and stakeholder groups, while conveying key messages about how the project can benefit and appeal to that specific group. Obtaining this information throughout the development of the project will help shape, and ultimately improve, the quality and relevance of its output. In this sense, the project is not done for stakeholders, it is built with them. Through this interaction, both project output and stakeholder groups can benefit, sharing

knowledge and results.

In the DoA, it is stated that enough activities should be organised, so as to engage each stakeholder group at least once per project year. This is a minimum requirement. With the various methods of engagement on offer, and the strong incentive to capitalise on the projects work, some groups may be engaged more. As well as this, the description of T3.1 within the DoA indicates that at least four online interactive sessions will be held across the course of the project.

To achieve these goals, the MES-CoBraD project has multiple methods of engagement at its disposal. These include the following: closed discussion groups; email consultation; 1-1 online consultation; survey; interactive workshops; webinar; open discussion group; longer events and conferences; twitter take over; Q&A sessions; and site open days. In the next sessions these methods will be proposed in relation to relevant stakeholder groups. These sessions each achieve different ends and can be catered for specific audiences, depending on how they are tailored, designed, and executed. This list is not exhaustive and may be developed throughout the course of the project.

Irrespective of the stakeholder group, the specific engagement methods proposed here are suggestions aimed at stimulating engagement during the project's cycle. Each group and session should be catered to the specifics of that group, the type of dialogue that is hoped to be achieved, and what stage the project is at, as well as what is being shared and asked for engagement on. These factors will always be considered prior to engagement, meaning the suggestions here are a base to work from, not a script to follow.

2.3 SEX AND GENDER WITHIN STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Issues relating to sex and gender have been given a high degree of importance throughout the project and this strategy hopes to maintain this focus, creating inter-project synergy, and conducting engagement activities with these standards in mind. As is also outlined in D3.4 (Sex and Gender analysis), this section discusses different strategic opportunities of mutual reinforcement between the sex and gender analysis and stakeholder engagement.

In medicine and mental health, the analysis of sex and gender cannot be reduced to sex aspects solely. Pinpointing differentiating factors between men and women both in biology and in the social, cultural, psychological, and territorial fields is the starting point for developing an increasingly accurate and articulated analysis that can lead to concrete recommendations for both medical practitioners and policy makers. Against this backdrop, engaging stakeholders regarding sex and gender aspects should occur horizontally across stakeholder categories, in such a way that stakeholders can understand how they, or issues within their field and areas of concern, affect and are affected by sex and gender aspects.

According to the European Institute for Gender Equality¹, a general gender stakeholder policy consultation can take two distinct forms:

- › 1. Consultations with stakeholders on the development, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of gender-equality policies;
- › 2. Consultations with stakeholders with a view to integrating a gender perspective into all general policies in all stages of the policy cycle.

More specifically, in relation to research in healthcare technologies, consultation with stakeholders can more fully highlight how sex and gender may influence “all stages of research and innovation, from strategic considerations for establishing priorities and building theory to more routine tasks of formulating

¹ EIGE (2019) *Gender stakeholder consultation*. European Institute for Gender Equality. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/mh0319274enn_002.pdf.

questions, designing methods and interpreting data”.² The goal of these interactions is to avoid pitfalls and to favor the emergence of new insights in terms of rethinking research priorities and outcomes, rethinking concepts and theories, formulating research questions, rethinking standards and reference models, and rethinking language and visual representations.

In practice, as much as we think that the issues of sex and gender are transversal to all categories of stakeholders, we envision focusing the sex and gender stakeholder consultation mainly the with **medical practitioners** (as is the focus of D3.3). Focus group interviews with medical practitioners will be conducted adopting the Capabilities and Vulnerabilities Approach (CVA).³ Put practically, CVA allows researchers to highlight the perceived strengths and weaknesses of an artefact (the medical technologies developed in MeS-CoBraD) in given contexts (the PUCs) to ascertain whether sex and gender variables determine different outcomes in terms of technology usage and whether other sociocultural variables, such as perceptions of healthcare systems, explain the technology’s strengths and weaknesses. Medical practitioners’ feedback will be used to ameliorate the technology.

2.4 STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

2.4.1 RESEARCHERS

2.4.1.1 Landscape

Researchers are a key group that will be targeted throughout the project. This was recognised in the survey as 87.5% of respondents indicated researchers are a main stakeholder group they intend to target with project activities. Due to the multidisciplinary nature of the project, the researchers who will be engaged will be diverse, spanning fields of medicine, engineering, and computer science, as recognised at the project’s outset. As well as this core group of researchers, those from social science, law, and philosophy will also be interested in elements of the project. Prior to specific activities, it is important to understand the diversity and difference amongst these research communities to properly engage them, as well as the opportunities of bringing them into dialogue.

This group can be broadly defined as individuals, or groups (as covered in research producing organisations section 2.1.2), involved in the production of research on issues associated with the MES-CoBraD project. The survey identified the following organisations as possible centres of engagement, showing the range of researchers that will be relevant for the project.

European Academy of Neurology⁴: A non-profit organisation with 45,000 members that connect national neurological societies, neurologists, and scientists. The organisations campaigns at a European level, as well as providing practical skills and knowledge for their members.

BGU Brain Imaging Research Centre⁵: This centre is located inside Soroka Medical Centre, Israel, and contains state-of-the-art MRI scanners, using them to treat patients and contribute to research.

Digital Ethics Lab, Oxford⁶: This research group is funded by Professor Luciano Floridi and focuses

² European Commission (2020), Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation – Policy Review, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union

³ Birks Lauren, Christopher Powell, Jennifer Hatfield (2017) Adapting the capacities and vulnerabilities approach: a gender analysis tool, Health Promotion International, Volume 32, Issue 6. Pages 930–941, <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/daw032>.

⁴ <https://www.ean.org/>

⁵ <https://in.bgu.ac.il/en/birc/Pages/default.aspx>

⁶ <https://www.oii.ox.ac.uk/people/luciano-floridi/>

on issues of computer ethics and the philosophy of technology.

Engagement of this group has already begun across the medical/scientific partners first round of stakeholder engagement meetings. They held closed discussion groups, inviting specific groups of stakeholders. Thus far two different researchers have been reached via closed discussion group meetings organised and hosted by the clinical partners.

For more specific information about the researchers targeted: Clinician scientists, as a key group of researchers, are involved both in research and clinical work with patients suffering from complex brain disorders. They have firsthand knowledge of difficulties in diagnosis, treatment, and complexity of CoBraD disorders. Their engagement will provide feedback through all stages of MES CoBraD project with their specialized experience and questions. The MES-CoBraD platform will provide vast amounts of RWD that can be accessed for future research protocols. Using data from the platform will minimize working hours in future projects since data could be easily withdrawn (e.g., neuropsychological tests, PSG).

Researchers involved in computer science and computer engineering are another group whose collaborations can be mutual beneficial. Through their engagement the sharing and reuse of analytical models developed by the project can be achieved and the unique model of real world data (RWD) expert systems can be shared openly to the wider benefit of the scientific community. Familiarity and experience with already existing platforms and models, as the one developed within MES-CoBraD, can provide valuable information since pros and cons from other platforms usage can be used as a guidance for MES-CoBraD platform.

2.4.1.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

Join the MES-CoBraD community to stay up to date with the latest developments in innovative treatment for complex brain disorders and ensure your research reflects the latest knowledge in the field.

Example of specific message for specific research groups, i.e., clinical researchers:

MES-CoBraD will provide access to RWD from patients, increasing the information database that can be used for future research projects, with minimized costs and providing tools that will improve accuracy of diagnosis, treatment, and comorbidity in CoBraD patients.

2.4.1.3 Engagement methods

The survey shows that partners already have existing communication channels and knowledge of engagement methods. Amongst those who expressed an intention to engage researchers (14 of 16 respondents), the two most common planned engagement methods were 1-1 consultation (face-to face or online) at 64.3% and closed discussion group, totalling 57.1% percent of those who planned to engage researchers. It is not possible to say if these engagement methods were recorded in the survey with particular stakeholder groups in mind, However, this does provide some clues as to thinking on engagement approaches.

Closed discussion groups will allow closed conversations amongst selected individuals/organisations who are invited personally. This forum is useful for discussing confidential information or thinking through processes while they are in development, as they are not open to a more general and wider audience.

Furthermore, a 1-1 consultation is similar in this sense, catering to a targeted individual in a way that is not open to a wider group.

In terms of engagement, and maximising engagement in a strategic and efficient way, conducting a workshop or webinar (online or in person) for researchers associated to MES-CoBraD could provide a method to begin a dialogue with these groups. This provides an opportunity for a wide audience to attend, participate, and give feedback. As researchers are a professional audience, this type of session allows them to acquire new knowledge which can be valuable for their work as well as engage and question based on their expertise. Furthermore, these sessions will allow for collaboration with other researchers as they can also be invited to present their work alongside MES-CoBraD project outputs. This has the potential to widen the audience and draw in another researcher's professional network.

Open sessions such as these cannot guarantee attendance, however the open nature allows additional stakeholder groups to be brought into dialogue creating a constant opportunity for cross stakeholder engagement. Attendance and promotion of these sessions must, as has previously been stated, work in conjunction with existing communication channels (see section 1.2.2). Furthermore, a comprehensive and up to date stakeholder database will provide a good contact base for targeted invitations to be sent.

2.4.2 RESEARCH PRODUCING ORGANIZATIONS (RPOs)

2.4.2.1 Landscape

Similar to researchers, as outlined above, research producing organisations (RPOs) will be important to the project. 43.75% of respondents indicated research producing organisations are stakeholders they would be targeting with their project activities. In this context, RPOs can be defined as organisations, or affiliated groups of researchers, that are involved in the production of research on issues associated with MES-CoBraD project. In practice, this could mean universities or groups that produce research.

The challenge in targeting this stakeholder category comes from its diversity. Institutions come in many different sizes, with a wide range of funding levels and expertise. Through engaging organisations that produce research, it is expected that individual researchers will also be reached, and vice-versa.

Examples of organisations, as identified by survey respondents:

Sagol Institute of Neuroscience⁷: As Israel's largest neuroscience school, they develop innovative research in collaboration with 170 research groups.

University of Athens, First Department of Paediatrics⁸: This department of the University of Athens deal with children's diseases and bring together researchers to produce scientific work.

Most of the Research Producing Organisations that work on the complex brain disorders being investigated by MES-CoBraD project share with the project similar goals, creating a natural synergy. However, many are in need of solutions that can be only achieved by more comprehensive analysis such is planned by the MES-CoBraD project.

RPOs, working on fields involved in the MES-CoBraD project, can contribute directly with their expertise and skills to better shape and develop our protocol and RWD database generation as long as they are in accordance with the benchmarks outlined in our project. Furthermore, the research-producing organizations can take advantage of the MES-CoBraD main outputs to develop their research questions and methodological approaches.

⁷ <https://en-sagol.tau.ac.il/>

⁸ <https://www.printo.it/pediatric-rheumatology/GB/center/172/University-of-Athens-Medical-School-Children-Hospital-Aghia-Sophia>

As was discussed in section 2.1.1.1, these RPOs targeted will mainly cover the core project disciplines – computer science, engineering, medicine.

2.4.2.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

Join the MES-CoBraD community to stay up to date with developments in innovative treatment for complex brain disorders and ensure your organisations research reflects the latest knowledge on the topic

Example of specific message for specific research groups, i.e., clinical researchers:

MES-CoBraD uses real-world data from multiple clinical sources through harmonized and practical protocols, as well as expert systems and artificial intelligence to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutics outcomes in patients. This methodology will contribute to the deep phenotyping of these relevant brain disorders improving research questions

2.4.2.3 Engagement methods

As outlined for the previous stakeholder group, researchers, within section 2.4.1.3, a webinar appears to be a suitable and effective way to engage with researchers. Due to the similarities with research producing organisations, this is also advisable and both stakeholder groups could be invited to the same session.

In addition, if specific RPOs are seen as targets with suitable output, they could be invited in a more direct way to engage in dialogue and through closed discussion groups or 1-1 consultation. The survey showed these are the favoured engagement methods of the consortium at this stage. Therefore, more work will be done to develop larger open events, such as workshops, webinars, and longer events. As it is clear, due to the survey, these methods are less familiar or less obviously applied to the project. This, however, depends on the nature of the organisation and the aims of that form of engagement.

RPOs are important for the impacts of MES-CoBraD to be fully actualised. These organisations share much in common with the stakeholder group researchers and there will be considerable overlaps. In this sense, there will also be various types of RPOs, mirroring the projects multi-disciplinary design. To engage these varied groups messages should be adjusted accordingly. Practically, RPOs are experts in particular fields and engaging them as experts is important, hence why webinars to present and share information are, at this stage, appropriate, logical, and effective means to capitalise on engagement with these groups.

2.4.3 RESEARCH FUNDERS

2.4.3.1 Landscape

As key drivers of research production, research funders are a key target group for the project achieve its potential and envisaged societal impact. Doing so could potentially create a legacy, beyond the project's lifecycle. With grant policies, funders can mandate and encourage the use of policies, practices, and tools developed by the project, meaning they are a significant ally in the uptake of proposed solutions. The survey showed that 18.75% of respondents claimed they would be targeting research funders with their activities. This figure suggests that the potential benefits of engaging this group are not widely

understood, or the ways to reach such groups is not immediately obvious. Here, the project can place additional focus.

The following example of research funders were provided by respondents to the survey:

Global Brain Health Institute⁹: Is an organisation dedicated to protecting the world's aging populations from threats to brain health. Amongst efforts to further health, they also fund research to develop new care-solutions.

Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO)¹⁰ is an independent funding body which falls under the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. The NWO ensures quality and innovation in science, within all disciplines and research fields. Its funds scientific research at public research institutions in the Netherlands, especially universities. The funds are allocated by means of a national competition on the basis of quality and independent assessment and selection procedures.

Engagement of this group has already begun across the medical/scientific partners first round of stakeholder engagement meetings. They held closed discussion groups, inviting specific groups of stakeholders. Thus far one research funder has been reached.

Research funders on the one hand need to be aware of the emerging MES-CoBraD work, provide input for its development and align with it. On the other hand, they are intermediaries and enablers through policies, calls for proposals and guidelines with who they fund. Thus, it is important to engage with research funding bodies of various levels and status (European/international/national, public/private, etc) and raise awareness on the project's goals and activities.

It is important to consider that research funding bodies operate at national level, since many European countries have research funding bodies that are operating on governmental budget and administration, or that are operating as third sector bodies. These will influence the way in which projects on complex brain disorders are perceived in relation to funded research.

What the project has to offer to research funding bodies, as well as the value for them, is twofold: they become part of creating the project's policy framework by actively contributing to MES-CoBraD, while the project will give them the chance to interact with other stakeholders, as well as providing the tools for them to readjust their funding policies.

2.4.3.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

MES-CoBraD will provide the new insights into cognitive brain disorders and their treatment. This will ensure policies are designed in the most efficient and effective way, matching the latest knowledge on this topic.

Ensure funding aligns with the latest developments in complex brain disorders, their understanding, and their treatment – participated in MES-CoBraD!

⁹ <https://www.gbhi.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/>

2.4.3.3 Engagement methods

Research funders are often national and international bodies, spanning multiple disciplines and funding projects throughout them. Therefore, engagement must be targeted and effective in order to capitalise on their time and achieve the projects wider societal aims and expected impacts.

Several channels and instruments have been identified to facilitate this engagement, including conferences and workshops, invitation sessions, and webinars. This fact could make a workshop a practical tool for hands on based experience with the eventual MES-CoBraD platform. These sessions serve as platform for research funders to meet & work towards alignment of funding policies made up of the stakeholders.

2.4.4 RESEARCH LIBRARIES

2.4.4.1 Landscape

Research libraries are institutions home to materials for research purposes, be they university libraries or national collections. Research libraries are organisations that provide support and training to researchers, with expertise on data management and publishing – two issues important for the MES-CoBraD project. With this training for researchers, it is possible for research libraries to provide validation and uptake of proposed solutions through their work, experience, and engagement of researchers. Overall, they are a vital component in the scholarly ecosystem.

18.75% of respondents stated they would be targeting to research libraries. This relatively low number shows that more should be done to understand the value of engagement with these groups, and the links to associated research libraries can be more deeply fostered. As research libraries are closely linked to researchers, they have a dual role as users and intermediaries. They are well placed to advocate for and raise awareness, support and train the researchers who may go onto use the MES-CoBraD platform.

Examples of these institutions given in the survey are:

EU Health Data Space¹⁴: As a European commission initiative, the goal is to make health data easily accessible for health care, health research, and policy making purposes.

Project beneficiary LIBER will provide a key link to these organisations. LIBER is a membership organisation for European research libraries, with over 450 associated and engaged members in its network. Furthermore, dedicated work groups, organised through LIBER, group library professionals on issues including data science, citizen science, and open access publishing. These provide channels into the library community via key experts on MES-CoBraD relevant topics allowing the engagement of this community to be more targeted. LIBERs proximity to research libraries will provide a key understanding of this stakeholder group as well as direct avenues to engage with them, resulting in an opportunity that is valuable for exploiting connections to this stakeholder group.

2.4.4.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

The MES-CoBraD project will develop tools and resources that can help libraries train their researchers who work on complex brain disorders. Be involved in this project and help understand how this tool can be used in your institution!

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/health/ehealth/dataspace_nl

Throughout the MES-CoBraD project, secure data sharing platforms and complex algorithms will be developed. Follow the work of the project to learn how these advances can be important for your institution.

2.4.4.3 Engagement methods

Research libraries are in contact with researchers who may benefit from the MES-CoBraD results and platform. This makes it crucial to engage with this community. Several channels and instruments have been identified to facilitate this engagement, including conferences and workshops, webinars, and surveys.

One clear way to engage with this group is LIBER's annual conference, which will be held in Denmark on 6-8th July, 2022. In addition, LIBER will share all events and activities with its library community to try and stimulate their engagement. This presents an opportunity to meet the requirements of engagement with this group, as well as understand how the project can be beneficial to them. In addition, LIBER also hosts other events, such as a Winter event, which enables extra opportunities for the project to create links with this community on topics such as open access publishing and data management.

2.4.5 INDUSTRY

2.4.5.1 Landscape

Private companies producing products, such as pharmaceutical companies or the medical informatics industry, have an important role in the MES-CoBraD project. 43.75% of respondents expressed an intention to target a desire to target industry with their activities. There are certain outputs of the project that sections of industry may see overlap and opportunities to collaborate and contribute to the project. Similar to research funders (see section 2.4.3), the engagement of the industry producing drugs and medical informatics technology can potentially increase the impact of the project beyond its end date.

Organisations that develop registries and treatment protocols may use RWD from the MES-CoBraD platform and other platforms for independent analysis in future projects and trials of products. Usage of Advanced Analytics modules, will be used in big data analyses within MES-CoBraD, providing up-to-date reports and novel approaches in interpreting results something that can be of benefit to large industries.

For organisations involved with other existing platforms, MES-CoBraD could help these industries develop and enhance interoperability across platforms and maximizing impact of data exchange and synergy. Developing advance consumer technologies will aid the future acquisition of RWD in a more cost-effective way that will be valuable to countries with limited resources. Current paper-to-database transfers are not cost-effective, requiring staff salaries, and risking errors during transfer. Digitalization of healthcare is imperative to optimize resources and output.

The following examples of organisations were provided in the survey:

LifeLine¹²: Company creating advance systems for neurophysiology recordings, and they constantly developing modern systems to update the quality and the effectiveness of neurophysiological monitoring. They will be happy to be members of the advisory board.

UCB¹³: Pharmaceutical company that have produced and distributed many standard drugs for the treatment of neurological disorders. They will follow the project progress and advice on linking

¹² <https://www.lifelinesneuro.com/>

¹³ <https://www.ucb.com/>

project results to development of new treatments

Madrija¹⁴: IT company designing and developing specific health information systems and integration services. They have experience in digital innovation and integration between health organizations and they can advice on sharing and handling medical data through the MesCobraD platform.

Engagement of this group has already begun across the medical/scientific partners first round of stakeholder engagement meetings. They held closed discussion groups, inviting specific groups of stakeholders. Thus far three different industry representatives have been reached.

2.4.5.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s): \

Get access to continuous generated RWD from patients, increasing the information database that can be used for future trials with minimized costs, and generate ideas on how to improve consumers technologies making RWD easier, accessible, and digitized.

2.4.5.3 Engagement methods

After the identification of industry groups relevant to the project, an engagement strategy needs to be pursued. Knowledge within the consortium should be able to scan for this network. Email consultation and closed discussion groups, methods favoured by the consortium should be a first point of entry to build relationships with these parties.

Once these relationships are established a broader type of engagement event would be preferable for sustained contact and engagement of these individuals and organisation. A webinar with results and the implications for industry could provide a forum to hear industry takes on project findings and begin to explore ways in which the project can respond.

2.4.6 POLICY MAKERS

2.4.6.1 Landscape

Policy makers, like the national or federal health agencies, are constantly pursuing new strategies to counteract diseases with high incidence or prevalence, like complex brain disorders studied by the MES-CoBraD initiative. To achieve this goal, these agencies need to rely on RWD acquisition and a deep understanding of the mechanism behind the physiopathology of these diseases. Therefore, the project will be of natural interest to policy makers. Likewise, the project should make efforts to reach this group, incorporating its perspectives, to meet its envisaged of societal impact.

56.25% of those who responded to the survey selected policy makers as a stakeholder group they would target with their project activities. Policy makers can be at the national or the European level of government. Specialist groups and organisations are also involved in policy discussions and decisions, providing their expertise. This somewhat blurs the definition of who makes policy, and how directly one must be involved with 'making policy' in order to be defined as a policy maker.

The following groups were provided as examples that could be reached with the project:

Epilepsy Nurse Association¹⁵: ESNA has a leading role in care of patients with epilepsy in the UK.

¹⁴ <https://www.madrija.com/es/>

¹⁵ <https://esna-online.org/>

They have experience on the unmet need of these patients group, and they are happy to advice on how the MesCobraD project could help in improving epilepsy patient's care.

LECE, Spanish League Against Epilepsy¹⁶. Following project progress and advice in aiming for the project to keep serving epileptic patients' improvement of care.

Overall, policy makers are viewed as an important group and their engagement with the project is essential. By participating throughout the project, the results and findings will be fully integrated and incorporated into policy decisions, and if this happens, societal benefits will be felt in the future.

2.4.6.2 Messages

The involvement of policy makers will be met by stressing the value of how the project outputs link to policy. These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

To ensure policy decisions are at the forefront of scientific research and best reflect the interest of your patients, join MES-CoBraD activities.

MES-CoBraD uses real-world data from multiple clinical sources through harmonized and practical protocols as well as expert systems and artificial intelligence will improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in patients. This methodology will contribute to the deep phenotyping of these relevant brain disorders and improve the development of new policies.

2.4.6.3 Engagement methods

Policy makers of different levels should be engaged with the project and its activities. Some sessions and outputs will be more relevant to them, and their input will help the project understand how to best make their work effective at a policy level.

The survey suggests that closed discussion groups and email consultations are the favoured methods of engagement. These are encouraged when building new relationships with key policy makers. However, interactive workshop, webinars, and meetings are felt to be appropriate for these groups. To maintain engagement from policy makers specialist engagement should take place in regular intervals rather than single events, making it easier to form long lasting impressions and consolidating new knowledge and policies.

If high level policy makers are engaged, it is important that their time and attention is utilised in an effective way. These individuals often managing competing demands and making their interactions and engagement with the project valuable is an important device in the success of engagement.

2.4.7 CITIZEN SCIENTISTS

2.4.7.1 Landscape

The participation and engagement of citizen scientists is becoming increasingly important as science becomes more open and transparent. Citizen science refers to “the general public engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort

¹⁶ <https://www.ilae.org/regions-and-countries/national-chapters/spain>

or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources” (Serrano et al., 2014).¹⁷ Citizen science generally refers to a broad network of people from different disciplines that have some experience in the field (e.g., some data skills in mathematics and social science), and help scientists in fields like development and deployment of technologies and education materials with the goal of unburdening the data scientists.

Citizen science is still emerging, and it is a concept still unclear to many (25% of survey respondents plan to engage this group) therefore the European Citizen Science Association (2015)¹⁸ definition of citizen science is helpful:

- Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates new knowledge or understanding;
- Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome;
- Both the professional scientists and citizen scientists benefit from taking part;
- Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process;
- Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project;
- Citizen science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for;
- Citizen science project data and meta-data are made publicly available and where possible, the results are published in an open access format;
- Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications;
- Citizen science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact;
- The leaders of citizen science projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution and the environmental impact of any activities.

Citizen scientists are active in various fields and ones associated to MES-CoBraD must be sought. The Woman Brain Project¹⁹ is one group that was proposed through the survey as a link to citizen science communities. On top of this, LIBER has a very active and relevant citizen science working group.²⁰

2.4.7.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

MES-CoBraD will provide access to RWD and an innovative platform that can support your scientific and research activities.

¹⁷ Serrano, F., Sanz, Francisco, Schaefer, Teresa, Silva, Cândida, & Kieslinger, Barbara. (2014). *White Paper on Citizen Science*. Retrieved from http://www.socientize.eu/sites/default/files/white-paper_0.pdf

¹⁸ https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/sites/default/files/ecsa_ten_principles_of_citizen_science.pdf

¹⁹ <https://www.womensbrainproject.com/>

²⁰ <https://libereurope.eu/blog/2019/03/28/explore-citizen-science-join-libers-newest-working-group/>

Engage with a community of leading scientists and software engineers on complex brain disorders, and explore how technology assists medical professions. Improve your science by joining the MES-CoBraD discussion

2.4.7.3 Engagement methods

Engagement with citizen scientists to receive feedback on their needs and user experience. In addition to expanding the project and its societal impact, it is important that citizen scientists are engaged to grow this field and empower citizen participation in scientific work.

A workshop presents an interesting opportunity to teach amateur scientists' and allow their enthusiasm to contribute to the session through practical activities, and prepared assignments. This also enables them to share their knowledge and contributions to this field. However, many other forms of engagement could prove interested with this particular group. For example, webinars may be interesting for these groups to learn about the project, as well as wider information based at the general public.

These activities largely depend on what level the citizen science groups operate and what type of expertise they hold. On one hand, they may be engaged at the level of researchers, if they possess expertise, whereas 'hobbyist' scientists or those supporting research may need different types of engagement activities. At this stage, only some relevant groups have been identified so further specification on this point cannot be provided. As groups are identified, their specifics will be assessed to ensure engagement is approached appropriately.

2.4.8 RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES & E-INFRASTRUCTURES

2.4.8.1 Landscape

The European commission defines research infrastructures and e-infrastructure as facilities that provide resources and services to research communities, allowing them to conduct research and innovate²¹. These may be single-sited, distributed, or virtual and can be deployed for education or public services, not simply research. This definition includes scientific equipment and instruments, collections such as archives and scientific data, and computing systems and communications networks. As demonstrated by the survey, 31.25% of respondents indicated they would target research infrastructures and e-infrastructure with project activities.

The following examples are given:

Life sciences RI²²: A European organisation that connects national research centres, technologies and expertise from industry and academia helping to facilitate research through access to such resources.

The Digital Ocean Community²³: An online community for software developers to share and communicate ideas. This online infrastructure connects developers and business to help them create software.

These sites and groups are highly diverse. Despite this, there are key benefits of engaging them throughout the project as equipment and knowledge within these groups is specialised, and site specific, which allows for unique perspectives and inputs. Due to their diversity, the benefits and avenues engagement of this group could provide is not yet clear and will depend on the sites that are engaged.

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures_en#:~:text=Research%20Infrastructures%20are%20facilities%20that,sited%2C%20distributed%2C%20or%20virtual

²² <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

²³ <https://www.digitalocean.com/community>

Although, the EOSC open science cloud²⁴ is another European initiative that could provide a strong and early link to an established e-infrastructure.

2.4.8.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

Be a part of the MES-CoBraD community and explore the possibilities of how the project can support Research Infrastructures, and how Research Infrastructures can help to build the project.

MES-CoBraD is an opportunity for Research Infrastructures to build bridges between their communities and MES-CoBraD outputs.

2.4.8.3 Engagement methods

Within the identified research infrastructures and e-infrastructures, the engagement methods should be catered for the specifics of that network. As some infrastructures, either physical or digital, connect networks of dispersed actors and equipment centres, a webinar to engage multiple members of these networks. By accessing multiple of these actors at the same time ensures more meaningful engagement with the infrastructure as a whole.

2.4.9 HEALTH PROVIDERS (PRIVATE & PUBLIC)

2.4.9.1 Landscape

Healthcare providers comprise of national healthcare programs, health maintenance organizations, hospitals, clinics, and healthcare work force itself. They are interested in new concepts, research, and innovation that impacts their daily clinical practice or the way they deliver healthcare. The MES-CoBraD project will provide new insights on these fields, making it a valuable relationship. Challenges these groups face include: micro and macro adaptations to innovations and ideas, limited resources (opportunity costs), competition with each other.

The contribution and engagement of these groups will benefit the project by sharing retrospective data, assisting recruitment efforts, identifying personnel with shared interests and adaptation of innovations/ideas. Health providers are vital to the project, and it must be ensured that they are involved throughout the project, not just with the project results. In the survey, 50% of respondents identified health providers as a group they would target with activities connected to the project.

Engagement of this group has already begun across the medical/scientific partners first round of stakeholder engagement meetings. They held closed discussion groups, inviting specific groups of stakeholders. Thus far six different health providers have been reached.

²⁴ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

2.4.9.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

The MES-CoBraD project will alter the way complex brain disorders are diagnosed, treated, and managed. Participate in this project to monitor developments and provide input on how this will affect patient care.

Scientific benefits may further improve earlier and more accurate diagnosis for patients with CoBraD and lead to identification of novel multidimensional RWD clinical and social outcomes that are of relevance to patients and their caregivers. They will further help assist care and improve clinical assessment and management.

2.4.9.3 Engagement methods

The type of engagement will depend on what needs to be discussed and what content must be shared. Closed discussion groups, conducted with targeted invites, would enable relationships to be build and developed as well as space for confidential or sensitive discussions. While this method limits engagement on a broader scale, it does create a forum for a deeper more personal connection. As these methods are favoured by the consortium, they appear a low hanging fruit to begin engagement with this group (as already has been seen)

When the project begins to produce findings that impact health providers in the way they care for patients, a session in which health providers share information about how this has affected their practice and approaches to complex brain disorders would be an ideal opportunity to demonstrate the work and impact of the project. This shows not only prior engagement, but the way the project has influenced practice. A session of this nature could take place in a webinar. A workshop may also allow the project to collaborate with a health provider, presenting to audience of other health providers, how the findings have changed their practice.

2.4.10 PATIENTS AND PATIENT ADVOCATES

2.4.10.1 Landscape

Patients and their advocates are gravely impacted by complex brain disorders and they are interested in leveraging new findings to immediately increase their personal or loved one's quality of life and mitigate personal or loved one's illness. This is contrary to research volunteers who are expected to take part in research from an altruistic perspective considering potential new discoveries. The volunteers are recruited from patients and patient group and recruitment typically occurs after establishment of a reciprocal trust system. This highlights the challenge of recruitment as patients are typically interested in what is available at the present and not what research may find, they are also typically less informed about brain health and diseases.

Patient and their advocates can leverage their power to influence other stakeholders such as health care providers and policy makers. They can encourage recruitment efforts through multiple ways. Despite these clear benefits, 37.5% of respondents intend to target patients and patient advocates. More links and connections can be sought with these groups, as they provide important feedback and insights into how medical research affects those that it is in place to eventually aid.

Examples of patients and patient advocates given included:

Fundacio Catalana de Síndrome de Down²⁵: A group of parents and professionals who aim to use research and first hand experience explore Down syndrome.

EYAL- Israel Epilepsy Association²⁶: Founded by the parents of children with Epilepsy, aiming to improve life quality of patients.

Engagement of this group has already begun across the medical/scientific partners first round of stakeholder engagement meetings. They held closed discussion groups, inviting specific groups of stakeholders. Thus far seven different patient groups have been reached. The project is important for these groups as they are building the data which the project is based upon and are a group that the outputs will ultimately shape better health outcomes for current and future members of this stakeholder group.

2.4.10.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s):

Our project will discover new ways to diagnose, treat, and manage your illness. Join the MES-CoBraD community to follow and contribute to advancing knowledge in this field!

MES-CoBraD aims to improve earlier and more accurate diagnosis for patients with brain disorders and lead to identification of novel multidimensional RWD clinical and social outcomes that are of relevance to patients and their caregivers. They will further help educate the public on brain health and improve clinical assessment and management.

2.4.10.3 Engagement methods

Groups of patients and advocate groups will be important groups to engage. Understanding their issues and perspectives will help the project achieve its desired societal impacts.

Patient open days are a method which should be utilised to engage this group and some partners already have experience of conducting similar activities. By creating open events at medical centres where patients can come and participate in sessions and learn about the project, you create the room for open-door engagement. Patients who have participated in project research activities should be encouraged to attend in order to maintain strong links to the project and show them the worth of their involvement.

Closed discussion groups for confidential matters or brainstorming sensitive issues. Depending on project activities and workflows, this type of engagement could be valuable for feedback. However, such sessions do not cater for mass engagement and are more focused.

To create broader engagement with these groups, webinars that target these groups to share specific information and outputs, as well as get specific input to further understand how societal objectives can be met with the needs of the patients.

2.4.11 GENERAL PUBLIC

2.4.11.1 Landscape

The MES-CoBraD project connects the world of health, research, and engineering, relying on RWD and aims in improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large by greatly

²⁵ <https://fcsd.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eyal-israeli-epilepsy-association/?originalSubdomain=il>

augmenting the diagnostic capability in complex brain disorders. The General public should stay alert to the project and its main developments and be informed of its outcomes since it can benefit largely from the improvements in their health that are beneficial. RWD acquisition is imperative for this projects development and apart from the clinically obtained we rely on everyday data provided by the general public and patients participating in the studies.

A way to engage this group is through the media, as well as social media, which will be explored throughout the project, as outlined in the communications and dissemination strategy (D9.1). However extra work will need to bring this group into dialogue and receive their input and thoughts on the project, it's activities and outputs. 31.25% of respondents are targeting the general public with project activities.

2.4.11.2 Messages

These groups can be targeted, reached, and encouraged to engage with the following message(s): 2

To help secure your health, your families, and the public at large, the MES-CoBraD project will work towards personalised medical approaches through the application of the platform it develops! Your involvement counts!

2.4.11.3 Engagement methods

For the above recommended engagement events that are based on open invitations, the public will always have the chance to attend. This hinges upon widespread communication and dissemination of sessions, allowing the general public to hear about events in the first place. However, their involvement cannot be guaranteed through only these channels. As stated, media options will be important to reach the wider public, who may not have a direct stake in the work of the project, at least at this moment.

A patient open day would be opportunity to engage the general public if the event is designed in this way. This is advisable as the general public may one day be patients with associated disorders, or family members of patients.

A twitter take-over session, in which a member of the project takes over the MES-CoBraD twitter and invites questions and shares their perspectives, is a way to engage a broader public, allowing questions by the public to reach specialist from beneficiaries. Furthermore, open-days at the universities and hospitals, that are members of the project, are opportunities to engage a broader public and present the work of the project.

2.4.12 OTHER GROUPS

2.4.12.1 Landscape

As well as the outlined groups, there are several other categories that could provide interesting sources of engagement that should not be overlooked. Here, these will be outlined. Owing to the fact this is a living document, new groups that are relevant to the project can also be included and focused on in the future, if project activities make these connections appropriate.

Three different beneficiaries, in responding to the survey, highlighted that they would like to target vulnerable groups such as people with disabilities or refugees. The nature of these groups is broad, and generalisations should not be made as local specifics and national situations will have a large bearing on the make-up of these groups. If the engagement of these groups is to be explored, local groups and associations with expertise and connections to vulnerable individuals should be used as a bridging point to build connections from.

Another point of engagement is other European projects. As part of WP9 a dissemination booster has

been pursued in order to connect MES-CoBraD to other associated projects. Though this tool, collaborations and co-organised events can be a promising engagement option. As well as inviting individuals from other projects to share knowledge with the MES-CoBraD consortium, project beneficiaries can make efforts to attend other project events and present information in these forums. This will create linkages and feedback channels that could provide not only dissemination options but key insights into how other projects operate and function which may be beneficial to MES-CoBraD.

3 CROSS STAKEHOLDER ACTIVITIES

3.1 OVERVIEW

A set of horizontal activities and actions are performed in the MES-CoBraD project, targeting more than one (potentially all) stakeholders. In order to reach project engagement KPI's – 1 engagement activity per year, per stakeholder group – the strategy of combining stakeholder groups within engagement is a key strategic approach to achieve this. In addition, the description of T3.1 indicates that at least four online interactive sessions will be held across the course of the project (for details and further planning of these sessions, see section 4.1) The natural synergies amongst stakeholder groups make targeting them in a combined manner a logical approach.

Facilitating engagement of this nature has benefits. Cross stakeholder engagement can create dialogue between groups and hold the potential of incorporating joined perspectives into the project work, creating new and unique input to consider. In other words, these activities create the opportunity for the cross-pollination of ideas and perspectives. In addition, some of the stakeholder groups outlined above have natural synergies and linkages which makes cross stakeholder engagement activities logical options to capitalise on sessions to engage a broader audience.

In the following sections, activities are proposed that combine stakeholder groups.

3.2 SUGGESTED ACTIVITIES

3.2.1 PLATFORM TRAINING WORKSHOP

The eventual platform that is developed by the MES-CoBraD consortium will be one of the central outputs of the project. As a new tool, it will need to be piloted and demonstrated to the stakeholders making up the intended users. As part of its development, it is necessary to test and pilot the tool, incorporating feedback from stakeholders which can be classified as engagement activities.

For example, stakeholders could be trained to a sufficient level to assess the effectiveness of the developed platform in order to advice for improvements. This could happen periodically in intervals of 6 months once the platform is developed in an initial format.

As the survey analysis outlined, four respondents have a provision for training stakeholders which relates to their research, results, and services as part of WPs and/or tasks. An additional four respondents indicated a need for training activities as part of their WPs and/or tasks but they have no provision to provide this.

More information about this event is provided in section 4.1.

3.2.2 IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH AND RESEARCHERS: WEBINAR

A natural overlap is present amongst the following stakeholder groups: researchers, research producing organisations, research funders, research libraries, and research infrastructures and e-infrastructures. To capitalise on this, a webinar delivered by the project should be designed and executed in order to engage these groups. During the session, a programme should be advised to thoroughly think through the implications of the project for research practices, research questions, future funding, and access to research equipment. Deliverables of scientific findings related to the project can be shared, with ample opportunity for the participants to share their knowledge and give feedback.

As has been acknowledged, these individual stakeholder groups are not homogenous, and differences exist within the research communities linked to the project. Due to this, a targeted session would help

reach specific research communities. The most appropriate partners to run this session and content which is best suited to the audience would have to be decided upon.

If this suggested session is pursued and successfully implemented, it would be helpful to run it on a bi-annual basis, with recurring participants. This would deepen the quality of engagement throughout the project.

As an important stakeholder group, more than one avenue to engage this group should be the goal. Despite this, a webinar to present project findings and outputs aimed at researchers presents a strong opportunity to both capitalise on engagement and reach the research communities in an appropriate way.

More information about this event is provided in section 4.1.

3.2.3 IMPLICATIONS FOR POLICY AND INDUSTRY: WEBINAR

Similar to the above suggestion, a synergy between stakeholder groups policy and industry could be a useful opportunity to align these two groups whose landscape analysis demonstrated they have similar interests in the project. The decisions of industry and policy in relation to the outputs of MES-CoBraD may be similar. For example: What implications does this have on treatment? What policy/products need to be updated related to project findings? Furthermore, these two groups have a stake in each other's perspective and responses to the MES-CoBraD project.

As has been acknowledged, these individual stakeholder groups are not homogenous. Therefore, the most appropriate partners to run this session and content which is best suited to the audience would have to be decided upon.

If this suggested session is pursued and successfully implemented, it would be helpful to run it on a bi-annual basis, with recurring participants. This would deepen the quality of engagement throughout the project.

More information about this event is provided in section 4.1.

3.2.4 IMPLICATIONS FOR PATIENTS AND HEALTH PROVIDERS: WEBINAR

Gaining patient and patient advocate perspectives, as well as the input of health providers, presents a valuable synergy for shared input and a key opportunity to bring two sides of the care environment into dialogue. It is expected that similar elements of the project will have implications, albeit different, for these groups. Above it was suggested that closed discussion groups could be used for these groups if confidential information should be discussed

More information about this event is provided in section 4.1.

3.2.5 WORK GROUP WEBINARS

As part of Work Package 4 (T4.1), working groups (WG) are established to allow the consortium to meet, discuss, and generate advances on specific topics. The aim is to improve the MES-CoBraD outputs as well as provide a space to incubate creative collaborations that may prove useful for specific research focuses. Currently the following nine groups are established, others may develop in the future: (1) Sleep work group; (2) neurodegeneration working group; (3) epilepsy working group; (4) neuropsychological testing working group; (5) magnetic imaging resonance working group; (6) biofluids and wearables working group; (7) machine learning and expert systems working group; (8) automatic quality control working group; and (9) user interface working group.

These groups provide an opportunity to engage stakeholders across the pre-identified groups, as outlined

above. The output from the groups can be presented in online sessions and webinars focused on specific topics, presenting the efforts and knowledge of that WG. Each group could use their efforts as ways to target stakeholders, however attention must be paid to which groups each topic could be relevant for. This information will become clearer as work group activities get underway, however an event could present an option to channel efforts towards.

Such activities could collaborate with WP9 in disseminating project work and simultaneously engage multiple stakeholder groups through interactive elements, with opportunity for feedback.

3.2.6 PROJECT CONFERENCE

A final project conference enables the total work of the project to be shared and communicated. This event would take place between M33 and M36 and would be combined with a large effort from WP9 and communication output. This type of event is also a strong opportunity for engagement across all stakeholder groups, as the event should be designed in such a way to incorporate all these perspectives. Coming at the end of the project's lifecycle, all stakeholders previously engaged and identified can be invited, building on the snowball sampling that has taken place. In addition to simply presenting MES-CoBraD work, stakeholders can be invited to present on how they have worked with the project or used MES-CoBraD themselves. If successful and effective, this activity would go to demonstrate the work of engagement throughout the project. However, this hinges on the success of engagement activities throughout the project and the relationships that the consortium can built with stakeholders.

To build upon this, a mid-project conference could be explored to assist with overall engagement of stakeholders and meeting KPIs. This would naturally take place around M18 of the project.

4 IMPLEMENTATION AND REPORTING

In this section, two items will be discussed. First, an outline and timeframe for four cross stakeholder engagement activities is provided. Second, a description of how management and reporting of engagement activities should be handled by the consortium.

4.1 ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES: PLANNING

The four online events stated in the DoA, under task 3.1, will be used as a way to ensure as many of the nine of the stakeholder groups are engaged as possible, and that the specific stakeholders who have been involved in the project prior to that stage have a chance to participate, learn about project progress, and offer their feedback and input. These activities were planned as being held online, due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, however, this will be reviewed prior to planning and delivery of these events.

Provisionally, these four events will be linked to the activities outlined in the cross stakeholder engagement section outlined above (section 3.2). At this stage, it is proposed that the platform training workshop, the webinars focused on implications for research and researchers, implications for policy and industry, and implications for patients and health providers, will make up these activities.

These events will take place between M12 and M24, at staggered intervals, involving partners closely connected, by nature of their organisation, with the specific stakeholder groups, and those with key information and outputs associated with that stakeholder group. Carrying out such activities in the second year of the project, mid-way through, is strategic in two ways. First, it allows a broad base of connections with stakeholders to have been established and ensures that they attend this event with enough knowledge of the project to engage in a meaningful way. Second, the second year of the project is a perfect time for stakeholder feedback to have a bearing in the future course of activities. It is important, for project aims to be met, that the input of key groups is heard and acted upon.

Following the publication of this strategy, efforts will be made to further the planning of these events, connecting with relevant members of the consortium, and creating content to ensure the engagement potential is met. In addition, this timeframe is largely dependent on the development process of the platform. Coordination with the technical partners will be required to understand when these activities can be conducted with a version of the platform.

4.2 REPORTING AND RECORDING ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Due to the range of potential stakeholder engagement activities – both outlined here and that emerge throughout the project – it is essential that each engagement activity is properly documented and recorded. This is necessary for measuring the effectiveness and impact of the project. Henceforth, this is a vital part of the strategic engagement process.

To do this, a shared file that allows members of the consortium to upload information about all engagement activities will be created and disseminated internally within the project. This spreadsheet will collect information including: event title, date, type of activity, number of attendees, the stakeholder categories of these attendees, if feedback from attendees was collected (if yes, links to the location of that feedback). Doing so will give a clear overview on performance of engagement as well as how the KPI's are being worked towards. This follow-up should also assist WP9 in post-event reporting and communication for project promotion.

Each partner will be responsible for inputting this information for engagement activities they organise. T3.1 leader (LIBER) will manage this file, monitor and review progress towards KPIs, and, eventually, report on this information in D3.7 Stakeholder Engagement Final Report (due M36).

5 RISKS AND MITIGATION

Potential risks which can hinder the success of the execution of the stakeholder engagement strategy are as follows:

5.1 PROJECT COMPLEXITY

The complexity of the project brings challenges. Moreover, the divide between scientific partners and the technical partners means that each group has different stakeholders, and different types of stakeholders within the categories, that are more relevant to themselves as an organisation and their outputs form the project. This makes strong project coordination essential, for the project's overall success, and that of the stakeholder engagement strategy.

While the MES-CoBraD project is complex and developments are continuous and simultaneous to the project activities, this Engagement Strategy has been drawn carefully making broad suggestions for what engagement methods fit particular groups. Additionally, few timelines have been added to create flexibility. The DoA states that enough activities should be organised, so as to engage each stakeholder group at least once per project year. Depending on the development of the project, these activities will be executed as is seen fit.

Internally, the project should properly use the stakeholder database to record what stakeholders are being targeted, who is targeting them, how have they been approached, and if there are existing links and connections to this group.

5.2 STAKEHOLDER RELUCTANCE AND MAKE-UP

Despite the work of this document, and best efforts of the consortium, the engagement of each stakeholder group cannot be taken as a pre-requisite. Here, the methods of engagement that are suggested are based on what is known about this group and the messages act as prompts to perk the interest of certain groups and show them the value or engaging with the project. As a living document, these messages can be adjusted if more effective messaging resonates with that particular group. Members of the project will do their utmost to reach all stakeholder groups in a thorough and meaningful manner, as it is important to reach the societal impact that is expected of the project.

The range of stakeholders outlined here, and the diversity within these categorisations, could potentially hinder the success of engagement activities. MES-CoBraD can, as has been justified, have various impacts within and outside of medical communities and certain stakeholders will be naturally interested in different parts of the project at different times. Owing to the multidisciplinary nature of MES-CoBraD, this also creates a more varied stakeholder landscape. The geographical diversity of the project also has implications for the stakeholder groups and the languages with which they can be accessed, this must be considered.

The diversity of stakeholder groups, both in make-up and geographically, means it is important for this document to take a living format. In this way, new information can be added, updating the contents based on specifics of that group – specifics which may become more apparent as the project continues. To overcome the challenges, it is important to target multiple groups within each category, as opposed to individuals or individual groups. This means the complexity is embraced and avoids too much emphasis being placed on one group.

5.3 COVID-19 PROTOCOLS

As the COVID-19 pandemic continues to (unpredictably) develop, engagement events must work within the parameters of what is safe, and what legislation and protocols allow at that time. The health situation will be monitored closely. In terms of events, provisions will be made for online events and appropriate

tools and platforms for engagement will be found and utilised.

5.4 GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION (GDPR)

How the project reaches out to individual stakeholders for engagement defined by General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The proposed stakeholder database aims to identify and leverage the existing knowledge and communication channels between project partners and groups within the target groups. Therefore, existing connections can be used to approach these groups. All project events, such as workshops or awareness raising webinars, will ask attendees when they sign up if they want more information about the project and ask for explicit permission to communicate with them further.

6 SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

This document has taken initial and substantial steps to creating a fertile base from which the project can properly engage with the groups and communities it set out to do, maximising the projects potential in reaching its scientific and societal goals. Each of the stakeholder groups have been clearly mapped and suggestions for how best to engage them based on their dynamics can guide the rest of the project.

As a living document, the proposed activities will be discussed concretely with partners and taken up where best applies. As this process develops, concrete engagement activities will be established, and discussions will focus on their outcomes. For each MES-CoBraD event, participants will be asked when signing up if they wish to participate in future events. This will aim to create continuous engagement from parties as the project develops.

Furthermore, post engagement-reporting on sessions (discussed in section 4.2) will reflect on the effectiveness of that form of engagement and seek feedback from those involved (in the case of bigger events) to fine-tune engagement endeavours. Understanding the impact of such sessions is difficult, and will be sought where possible, but active reflection and learning will ensure the engagement of stakeholders is improved throughout the project.

Following this deliverable, an internal stakeholder database will be created, as has been earlier referenced. Each project beneficiary will be asked to add to and update a list of contacts, assigning them to stakeholder categories. They will be encouraged to make use of existing networks and communicate to these individuals/organisations opportunities for engagement and try and create links and engagement with these parties. Through creating an internal stakeholder database, each beneficiary will be encouraged to think about utilising their knowledge. This will help the project reach its target of at least one engagement session with each group, per year. Practically, when events and sessions are organised, this database will provide a reference point.

Overall, the importance of stakeholder engagement has been stressed repeatedly and with this outline the project can begin to move forward with exploiting the potential of its outputs in dialogue with key stakeholders.

Annex I : Stakeholder Engagement Survey

MES-CoBraD: T3.1 Stakeholder Engagement Survey

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

MES-CoBraD T3.1 Internal Survey

Activity: Internal survey for stakeholder landscape analysis.

Purpose: This internal survey is led by T3.1 Stakeholder engagement. It targets all project partners and aims to map the overall stakeholder landscape across the MES-CoBraD project.

Based on the information you will provide, the T3.1 LIBER will organise targeted meetings per WP or task, depending on needs. Please complete all questions, providing as clear and detailed information as possible.

Time-frame: The survey must be completed no later than 29/06/21.

Instructions: All questions marked with * are mandatory. Please make sure that at least one person from your organisation takes this survey. If different colleagues from your organisation are involved in different WPs/Tasks, we welcome more than one reply per organisation.

A. Partner Identification

• 1. I am filling out this survey on behalf of:

- CLALIT HEALTH SERVICES (CHS-RMC)
- CYBERETHICS LAB SRLS (CEL)
- ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA (ENG)
- FUNDACIO PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU (IR-HSCSP)
- HOLISTIC IKE (HOLISTIC)
- KING'S COLLEGE LONDON (KCL)
- MICHPOULOS I. & CH. G.P. (EVOLUTION)
- NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS - NTUA (NTUA)
- Neurological Institute of Athens (NIA)
- SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL (SIMAVI)
- STICHTING LIBER (LIBER)
- THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH (UEDIN)
- UPPSALA UNIVERSITET (UU)
- VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL (VUB)

• 2. Full name:

1

• 3. Email:

• 4. I am a Work Package (WP) leader:

- Yes
- No

4.1 If yes, which WP:

- WP1
- WP2
- WP3
- WP4
- WP5
- WP6
- WP7
- WP8
- WP9

• 5. I am a task leader:

- Yes
- No

5.1 If yes, which task(s):

- T1.1 – Project Management and Quality Monitoring
- T1.2 – Administrative and Financial Management
- T1.3 – Technical Coordination
- T1.4 – Scientific Coordination
- T1.5 – Innovation Management
- T2.1 – The CoBraD legal and ethical framework
- T2.2 – The CoBraD PUC legal and ethical assessment
- T2.3 – The CoBraD Legal & Ethics Helpdesk
- T2.4 – IPR and standardization issue
- T3.1 – Stakeholder Engagement
- T3.2 – Harmonization and Interoperability Protocol of CoBraD RWD Acquisition and Sharing
- T3.3 – Quality and Quantity Data Validation
- T3.4 – Methodology Elaboration
- T3.5 – Sex and Gender analysis and impact assessment
- T3.6 – ETHAI model of AI in healthcare ethics standard development
- T4.1 – Distribution of Planned Analyses for Hypothesis Testing – Collaborative Multidisciplinary Research WorkGroups
- T4.2 – Existing Hypothesis and Planned Analyses Re-evaluation and Updating per Latest Literature

- T4.3 – CoBraD Multisource Multidisciplinary Exploratory & Confirmatory Planned Data Analyse
- T4.4 – Dynamic Advanced Analytics Research Framework – MES-CoBraD Deep Learning and Machine Learning DataAnalyses
- T4.5 – Communicate Result Novelty and Impact to Expert System Developers and Dissemination ParticipatingOrganizations – Scheduled and On-demand
- T5.1 – Data integration and harmonization for heterogeneous data source
- T5.2– Security and Anonymisation Framework
- T5.3 – Sharing and re-use of data and algorithm
- T6.1 – Expert Systems
- T6.2 – Data Analytics & Visualisations
- T6.3 – Artificial Intelligence
- T7.1 – Specifications and requirements for system integration and development cycle
- T7.2 –Infrastructure design and preparation
- T7.3 – System Continuous Integration and Testing
- T7.4 – System Validation and Verification
- T8.1 – Participant recruitment and pre-existing RWD access
- T8.2 – Implementation of the Multidisciplinary Protocol CoBraD& Pilots Evaluation
- T8.3 – Secure RWD sharing
- T9.1 – Dissemination and communication strategy
- T9.2 – Promotional and informational material
- T9.3 – Online presence
- T9.4 – Opportunity-based promotion of the project – Connecting to Society
- T9.5– Business and Exploitation Planning

• 6. Which academic disciplines/branches are the most relevant for your WP/task? Please note that this is a non-exhaustive list. Please choose as many as apply to your activities.

- Humanities/Law
- Social Sciences/Anthropology
- Social Sciences/Economics (behavioural, neuroeconomics, public, welfare)
- Social Sciences/Geography (human, health)
- Social Sciences/Political Science (policy, public administration, civics)
- Social Sciences/Psychology (biological, clinical, cognitive, health, medical, neuro, behavioural, social)
- Social Sciences/Sociology
- Social Sciences/Social work (clinical, community practice, mental health, psychosocial rehabilitation, person-centered therapy, family therapy, financial social work)
- Natural Sciences/Biology (bioinformatics, biotechnology, computational, genetics, immunology, pathology, physiology, neurobiology, virology)
- Natural Sciences/Chemistry (biochemistry, chemical engineering, cheminformatics, immunochemistry, medicinal, neurochemistry)
- Formal Sciences/Computer science (AI, data science, software engineering)
- Applied Sciences/Business
- Applied Sciences/Engineering & technology (chemical engineering)
- Applied Sciences/Medicine and health (clinical, epidemiology, geriatrics, health informatics, cardiology, neurology, pathology, pharmaceutical sciences, psychiatry, sleep medicine, speech-language pathology, surgery)

6.1 If other, please specify:

B. Stakeholder Identification

In this section, we want you to identify the specific stakeholders that you aim to target with the activities you lead or participate in.

- 1. Which main stakeholder groups, as identified at the proposal stage, are you targeting with your activities? (TG - Target Group)

- TG1: Researchers
- TG2: Research producing organisation
- TG3: Research funders
- TG4: Research libraries
- TG5: Industry
- TG6: Policy makers
- TG7: Citizen scientists
- TG8: Research infrastructures (RIs) and e-infrastructure
- TG9: Health providers (public and private)
- TG10: Patients and patient advocates
- TG11: General public
- Other

- 1.1. If other, please specify:

500 character(s) maximum

- 2. Which of the main stakeholder groups are your primary target?

- TG1: Researchers
- TG2: Research producing organisation
- TG3: Research funders
- TG4: Research libraries
- TG5: Industry
- TG6: Policy makers
- TG7: Citizen scientists
- TG8: Research infrastructures (RIs) and e-infrastructure
- TG9: Health providers (public and private)
- TG10: Patients and patient advocates
- TG11: General public

- 3. Have you identified any specific sub-groups of the aforementioned main stakeholder groups, that are critical for your WPs/tasks? Indicative format for your reply: "main stakeholder group/subgroup". Example: TG10: patients and patient advocates/Dementia

2000 character(s) maximum

- 4. Please identify (per stakeholder group) any established organisation, group of organisations or initiative at national/international level that you consider important for the work of MES-CoBraD, which your organisation is already engaged with. If you are targeting individuals that do not belong to an organisation, please note them as "individuals". Please provide the engagement channels you have in place to contact them. Indicative format for your reply: "name of organisation: we both participate in working group x". Examples of engagement channels could include: working group, interest group, organisation board, collaborating on a project as project partner. For the TGs that do not apply to you, please respond "N/A".

4.1. TG1: Researchers

2000 character(s) maximum

• **4.2. TG2: Research producing organisations (RPOs)**

2000 character(s) maximum

• **4.3. TG3: Research funders**

2000 character(s) maximum

• **4.4. TG4: Research libraries**

2000 character(s) maximum

• **4.5. TG5: Industry**

2000 character(s) maximum

• **4.6. TG6: Policy makers**

2000 character(s) maximum

• **4.7. TG7: Citizen scientists**

2000 character(s) maximum

• 4.8. TG8: Research infrastructures (RIs) and e-Infrastructures

2000 character(s) maximum

• 4.9. TG9: Health providers (public and private)

2000 character(s) maximum

• 4.10. TG10: Patients and patient advocates

2000 character(s) maximum

• 4.11. TG11: General public

2000 character(s) maximum

• 5. Are there vulnerable groups (e.g., refugees, disabled persons) who you would like to reach/engage with the project?

- Yes
- No

5.1. If yes, please specify:

2000 character(s) maximum

C. Stakeholder Engagement

In this section we aim to map all the activities needed to engage your stakeholders.

• 1. What type of engagement activities are you planning to organise during the project?

- Closed discussion group (by invitation only)
- Open discussion group (public invitation)
- 1on1 (face to face or online) consultations
- Email consultations and follow-ups
- Interactive workshop (1-1,5h)
- Webinar (1h)
- Longer event (e.g., half-day)
- Survey
- Other

1.1. If other, please specify:

2000 character(s) maximum

- 2. Are the aforementioned engagement activities specified under the description of the WPs/Tasks you are working on?

- Yes
- No

- 3. Are the aforementioned engagement activities linked to a specific deliverable?

- Yes
- No

3.1. If yes, please specify. Indicative format for your reply: "meetings with stakeholders to get input for DX.X"; "workshop to discuss results of DX.X. with relevant stakeholders."

500 character(s) maximum

- 4. How frequently do you need to engage with the aforementioned stakeholder groups?

- More than once per month
- Monthly
- Every other month
- Every 6 months
- Once per year
- Once overall
- Random

D. Training

In this section we want to map training activities targeting your stakeholders

- 1. In the WPs/Tasks you participate in, is there a provision for training of the stakeholders you are targeting, related to your research/results/services?

- Yes
- No

1.1. If yes, please specify the task(s) this training is linked to and the specific stakeholder categories it targets:

500 character(s) maximum

- 2. In the WPs/Tasks you participate in, is there a need for training for the stakeholders you are targeting, but no provision?

- Yes
- No

2.1. If yes, please specify the task(s) this training is linked to and the specific stakeholder categories it targets:

500 character(s) maximum

• 3. Is the aforementioned training linked to a specific tool/service that the project will develop/upgrade?

- Yes
- No

3.1. If yes, please specify the task this tool/service is linked to and the month it is expected to be delivered and the specific stakeholder categories it targets:

500 character(s) maximum

• 4. Please mark the types of training events:

- Face to face training
- Webinar
- Monitoring/peer learning
- Train the trainer event
- Other
- N/A

4.1. If other, please specify:

500 character(s) maximum

• 5. Please mark the types of training materials:

- Factsheet(s)
- FAQs(s)
- Tutorial
- Case studies
- Other
- N/A

5.1. If other, please specify:

500 character(s) maximum

E. Opportunity-based communication

Opportunity-based communication utilizes existing communication channels, events, and initiatives as means to promote the project.

- 1. Which upcoming events/conferences are you aware of that are relevant for the project? I.e., opportunity for attendance, presentations, co-located events. Please specify the name of the event/conference and the main stakeholders to be targeted.

2000 character(s) maximum

- 1.1. Of the events/conferences specified above, which are suitable for a co-located event(s)?

2000 character(s) maximum

- 2. Which dissemination means do you already have in place for communicating with your stakeholders?

- Newsletter
- Social media
- Mailing list
- Journal
- Press releases
- Other

- 2.1. If other, please specify:

500 character(s) maximum

- 3. Which external specialised journals/newspapers/other media can you propose that the project needs to target for dissemination material?

2000 character(s) maximum

- 4. Which relevant initiatives/projects are you aware of that can be targeted for cross-promotional activities?

2000 character(s) maximum

- 5. Could the WPs/Tasks you participate in be the starting point for a citizen science activity?

- Yes
- No

- 5.1. If yes, please specify WP/task:

500 character(s) maximum

Privacy and Data Management

This is an MES-CoBraD internal survey. Information and data shared will be treated with confidentiality in the context of the project and will be stored in its designated area. No contact information of stakeholders is being collected.

